

1 **COVID-related anthropause highlights the impact of marine traffic but not tourists on**
2 **breeding little penguins**

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19

20 **Abstract**

21 The COVID-19 pandemic and its lock-down measures have resulted in periods of reduced
22 human activity, known as anthropause. While this period was expected to be favorable for the
23 marine ecosystem, due to a probable reduction of pollution, shipping traffic, industrial activity
24 and fishing pressure, negative counterparts such as reduced fisheries surveillance could
25 counterbalance these positive effects. Simultaneously, on-land pressure due to human
26 disturbance and tourism should have drastically decreased, potentially benefiting land-based
27 marine breeders such as seabirds. We analyzed 11 breeding seasons of data on several biological
28 parameters of little penguins from a popular tourist attraction at Phillip Island, Australia. We
29 investigated the impact of anthropogenic activities on penguin behavior during the breeding
30 season measured by (1) distribution at sea, (2) colony attendance, (3) isotopic niche (4) chick
31 meal mass, and (5) offspring investment against shipping traffic and number of tourists. The
32 2020 lock-downs resulted in a near absence of tourists visiting the Penguin Parade®, which was
33 otherwise visited by 800,000+ visitors on average per breeding season. However, our long-term
34 analysis showed no effect of the presence of visitors on little penguins' activities. Surprisingly,
35 the anthropause did not triggered any changes in maritime traffic intensity and distribution in the
36 region. We found inter- and intra-annual variations for most parameters, we detected a negative
37 effect of marine traffic on the foraging efficiency. Our results suggest that environmental
38 variations have a greater influence on the breeding behavior of little penguins compared to short-
39 term anthropause events. Our long-term dataset was key to test whether changes in
40 anthropogenic activities affected the wildlife during the COVID-19 pandemic.

41 **1. Introduction**

42 With the development of human activities, ecosystems can no longer be considered as
43 undisturbed and independent entities (Mace, 2014), leading to the concept of socio-ecological
44 systems (Everard, 2020; Wei et al., 2018). Because of the numerous interactions at stake, socio-
45 ecological ecosystems are often complex to analyze (Sugihara et al., 2012). The quasi-
46 continuous presence of humans in most, if not all, ecosystems make it challenging to understand
47 the full impact of anthropogenic activities on the environment.

48 In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic led to periods of lock-downs that resulted in a major
49 reduction of human activities and movement at both local and global level, a period coined as the
50 “anthropause” (Lamers and Student, 2021; Rutz et al., 2020). The anthropause created an
51 opportunity to quantify the impact of human activities on wildlife. To date, studies found both
52 negative and positive effects of this anthropause on wildlife, through for example, increase of
53 predators presence and disturbance on an iconic seabird colony in the Baltic Sea (Hentati-
54 Sundberg et al., 2021), as well as increased species richness in less-disturbed areas (Manenti et
55 al., 2020). Lock-downs also led to increased illegal hunting and plastic pollution, and reduced
56 conservation efforts with negative effects on wildlife (Bates et al., 2021; Kadykalo et al., 2022).
57 In a comparative study, Bates et al. (Bates et al., 2021) showed that despite the decrease in
58 humans’ movement, or industrial activities, the median responses of wildlife to anthropause were
59 centered on 0, because either positive and negative effects balanced themselves, or for numerous
60 species, no effects were observed.

61 Moreover, it can be misleading to consider that the anthropause is a phenomenon
62 homogeneously distributed across the globe. The decrease in human activities was not equal
63 across the planet (Bates et al., 2021), calling for more studies across ecosystems.

64 However, it can be complex to study the dynamics of entire ecosystems, specifically within the
65 context of the COVID lock-downs, considering the difficulties to carry on with species and
66 habitat monitoring activities during these periods. Monitoring “sentinel species” helps tackling

67 this issue. Sentinel species integrate changes happening across ecosystems' levels (Durant JM et
68 al., 2009), integrate broader processes into rapidly interpretable metrics, are simpler to study, can
69 respond rapidly to environmental changes and cover a large spatial scale (Bost et al., 2008;
70 Durant JM et al., 2009; Hazen et al., 2019; Siddig et al., 2016). Therefore, long-term dataset on
71 marine predators, especially seabirds, are often used as indicators of ecosystems' changes
72 (Cairns, 1988; Furness and Camphuysen, 1997; Piatt et al., 2007b).

73 Data collection via continuous monitoring programs allows researchers to compare the pace of
74 parameters responses to global changes and assess effects of human pressure on wild populations
75 (Cairns, 1988; Durant JM et al., 2009; Einoder, 2009; Ramírez et al., 2017; Tucker et al., 2019,
76 2018). Techniques used vary depending on the research question and feasibility, comprising of
77 visual observations, counts, nest monitoring, blood sampling and use of bio-logging techniques.
78 In seabirds, chick growth, colony attendance, and individuals' activity budgets vary at different
79 temporal scales and in relation to both environmental and human activities (Cairns, 1988).
80 Depending on the specific effects of the COVID lock-downs and the relative short period these
81 were put in place, some of these traits might show no responses to anthropogenic pressure
82 (Cairns, 1988; Piatt et al., 2007a).

83 During breeding season, seabirds are central place foragers exploiting food resources
84 around their breeding colony to which they return due to reproductive requirements (e.g., egg
85 incubation, chick provisioning), hence alternating between nest attendance and foraging trips
86 (Einoder, 2009; Piatt et al., 2007b; Saraux et al., 2011b). Seabirds must cope with constraints of
87 living in two different environments, feeding at sea and breeding on land, making them exposed
88 and vulnerable to threats from both land and sea. The little penguin (*Eudyptula minor*) is the
89 smallest penguin species endemic of Australia and New Zealand (BirdLife International, 2023).
90 Phillip Island, Australia, holds one of the largest little penguin colonies in the world with a
91 population estimated between 28,000 and 32,000 individuals (Sutherland and Dann, 2014). The
92 colony located at the "Penguin Parade ®" receives the visit of hundreds of thousands of tourists

93 per breeding season, especially when little penguins return ashore at night (Dann and Chambers,
94 2013). The “Penguin Parade ®” is a nature park, where considerable efforts have been made to
95 manage tourism so as to avoid affecting breeding penguins. Yet, it has been running everyday
96 since 1968, with an average of half a million visitors per year, making it difficult to test whether
97 penguins are disturbed by the presence of humans. At sea, little penguins can also interact with
98 maritime traffic such as commercial shipping, recreational or commercial fishing vessels
99 (Cannell et al., 2020; Crawford et al., 2017). Land introduced predators and starvation are the
100 major causes of little penguins’ mortality, but collision with vessels were also reported (Cannell
101 et al., 2020, 2016), even though their foraging range is small (around 30 km for single day trips
102 but can be up to 214 km for multi days trips) (Collins et al., 1999; Poupart et al., 2017; Sánchez
103 et al., 2018).

104 On land, tourism has been shown to affect various parameters of penguins’ ecology such as
105 stress level, reproductive output (Ellenberg et al., 2007) or behavior (Colombelli-Négrel and
106 Katsis, 2021; Ellenberg et al., 2007; French et al., 2019). At-sea, vessels can directly (Pichegru et
107 al., 2022) or indirectly (Mattern et al., 2013) affect penguins foraging through noise pollution
108 and deterioration of the environment, respectively. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Australia
109 underwent a series of rigid lock-downs, drastically reducing anthropogenic activities. During
110 most of that period, the “Penguin Parade ®” remained closed to the tourists, providing a good
111 opportunity to understand if the anthropause affected ecology of little penguins. At a moment
112 when ecotourism is often the key to the acceptance of stakeholders for conservation programs,
113 this could provide important answers to the effect of highly-managed tourism.

114 We investigated whether the anthropause affected metrics linked to little penguin's behavior
115 during the breeding season in 2020 (with lock-downs) by comparing against 10 breeding seasons
116 of population monitoring and movement data (2010-2019) to 2020. The studied colony has been
117 monitored for the past 23 breeding seasons using an automated penguin monitoring system (date,
118 time and weight of penguins recorded when leaving and arriving to the colony), with daily count

119 of penguins arrival at dusk, and with the use of bio-logging techniques (the latter since 2010)
120 (Ramírez et al., 2015). We tested whether reduced anthropogenic activities influenced little
121 penguins (1) at-sea activity by studying their at-sea distribution, overlap with marine traffic,
122 isotopic diet (in terms of prey type and quantity), and (2) on-land activity by studying their
123 colony attendance (departure and arrival time), and meal size given to their chicks. We
124 considered the daily number of tourists at the Penguin Parade ® as a proxy of land disturbance,
125 and the number of vessels and their overlap with little penguins' foraging area at-sea as a proxy
126 of the at-sea disturbance. We hypothesized that when land disturbance was reduced during the
127 anthropause, due to the absence of tourists in the parks, little penguins would change their colony
128 attendance pattern by coming and leaving more synchronously, as they will not have to avoid
129 tourist disturbance (Klomp and Wooller, 1991; Rodríguez et al., 2016). Moreover, if the
130 anthropause reduced the at-sea disturbance, little penguins would display a higher foraging
131 efficiency as the overall marine environment and its species will be less disturbed by the traffic,
132 through reduction in noise pollution for instance (Pichegru et al., 2017, 2010).

133 **2. Material and Methods**

134 2.1 Study site and long-term monitoring of foraging behavior

135 The study was conducted on the little penguin breeding colony at Penguin Parade, Phillip Island,
136 Australia (38°21'S, 145°09'E) from 2010 to 2020. The breeding season of little penguins occurs
137 in the austral spring and summer, from September to December.

138 For the period of our study (11 breeding seasons, 2010-2020), penguins were captured from their
139 nest boxes and equipped with GPS loggers (Axy-Trek, Italy, Mr Lee, China) recording positions
140 at 120 s interval for incubation and postguard trips and every 20 s for guard trips (supplementary
141 table 1). Loggers were attached to their lower backs with Tesa ® tape (Wilson et al., 1997). After
142 returning from their foraging trips, penguins were recaptured at the colony and the logger
143 retrieved. Handling time was kept at less than 5 min. Details of the logger deployment are
144 described in Pelletier et al. (2014), and Barreau et al. (2021). We combined the information
145 obtained from GPS data for estimating the distribution of little penguins at sea, stable isotopes
146 data to investigate their diet, as well as from the automated monitoring system to track changes
147 in body mass and colony attendance.

148 Two automated penguin monitoring systems (APMS) are placed on the main pathways between
149 the little penguins' colony and the beach. When walking through APMS, little penguins are
150 individually identified with passive transponders (Allflex, Australia) that had previously been
151 inserted in the back of the penguins, either as chicks or the first time they were encountered in
152 the colony. In addition, APMS record date, time, direction of passage, and the body mass of the
153 individuals (Joly et al., 2022).

154 This research was conducted under the Phillip Island Nature Parks Animal Experimentation
155 Ethics Committee approval and a research permit issued by the Department of Environment
156 Land, Water and Planning of the state of Victoria, Australia.

157 2.2 Data manipulation and analysis

158 Data manipulation and analysis was done in R v4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2023). All scripts used in
159 this analysis are available upon request (Github link removed for anonymity). Unless specified
160 otherwise, results indicate mean and standard error. As well, when more than one variable was
161 considered within a model, all model combinations were tested, and we performed model
162 selection using Akaike's information criterion (AIC) (Bozdogan, 1987). The model with the
163 lowest AIC was considered as best. Normality of residuals, residual autocorrelation and
164 homoscedasticity were checked graphically. We considered p-values under 0.05 as significant.
165 Unless stated otherwise, pairwise post-hoc comparisons were performed using Holm p-value
166 correction (Holm, 1979).

167

168 2.3 GPS data processing

169 A foraging trip was defined as a period from the departure to the return to the colony. Because
170 little penguins are visual hunters, foraging activities only occur during daylight (Cannell and
171 Cullen, 1998; Chiaradia et al., 2007). Their foraging trips last typically between 1-9 days during
172 incubation (Kato et al., 2008), 1 day during guard (Pelletier et al., 2014) and between 1-17 days
173 during post-guard (Saraux et al., 2011a). During guard, parents alternate trips at sea, while in
174 post-guard, chicks are left unattended in the colony (Saraux et al., 2011b). From each foraging
175 trip, and day out at sea, we extracted a "foraging segment", intended as the period between
176 nautical dawn and nautical dusk. Therefore, one-day trips contained only one foraging segment,
177 while multiple-days trips could contain several segments. We removed foraging segments with
178 less than 3 GPS locations, and segments starting after sunrise or stopping before sunset, from the
179 analysis. Overall, out of 233 foraging trips, a total of 371 foraging segments were extracted and
180 analyzed (range 1-7 segments per individual).

181 We calculated the distance between each consecutive location on the WGS ellipsoid using the
182 *pointdistance()* function from the "raster" R package (Hijmans, 2022). Swimming speed was
183 then calculated between two consecutive locations as the distance divided by the time interval.

184 Furthermore, we excluded GPS locations with swimming speed higher than 8 km.h⁻¹ (i.e., max
185 swimming speed of little penguins, Watanuki et al., 2006), or with a time interval between 2
186 consecutive GPS locations lower than 7.2 sec (i.e., duplicated points). GPS locations can be
187 obtained only when penguins resurface, therefore it is necessary to interpolate raw GPS data and
188 reconstruct their path. For each foraging segment, we regularized the time interval between each
189 location by performing spatial interpolation at 15-min interval using the correlated random walk
190 algorithm within the *crawlWrap()* function from “MomentuHMM” R package (McClintock and
191 Michelot, 2018).

192 Interpolated foraging segments were projected into the GDA94 / Australian Albers projection.
193 For each breeding season, we then used the *kernelUD()* function from the “adehabitatHR” R
194 package (Calenge, 2006) to calculate 50% (core area), and 95% (homerange) kernel utilization
195 distribution (UD). The smoothing parameter *h* was calculated using the ad hoc method (Seaman
196 et al., 1998).

197

198 2.4 Stable isotope data processing

199 To describe the isotopic niches of little penguins and examine differences between 2020 and
200 previous breeding seasons (2010-2019), we analyzed $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ stable isotopes from 842
201 blood samples (n = 196 in incubation, n = 367 in guard, n = 279 in post-guard). Values in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$
202 increase with prey trophic level, while $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values are higher inshore than offshore (Hobson et
203 al., 1994). We followed the protocol described in Chiaradia et al. (2016). Whole blood was
204 freeze-dried and then powdered. As mass C/N ratios were all below 3.5, there was no need for
205 correction of lipid contents in whole blood (Post et al., 2007). Isotopic analysis was then
206 performed by means of a Robo-Prep elemental analyzer coupled to a Europe 20:20 continuous-
207 flow isotope ratio mass spectrometer. Based on replicate measurements of within-run standards,
208 measurement error was estimated to be ± 0.3 and $\pm 0.1\text{‰}$ for $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ measurements,
209 respectively.

210

211 2.5 Automated penguin monitoring system

212 We evaluated two measures of body mass variation. First, we calculated the mass gained after a
213 foraging trip, which we considered to be an estimate of foraging efficiency (Saraux et al., 2011a).
214 Two body masses were considered belonging to the same foraging trip when their records were
215 consecutive in date and time for a given transponder number and the trip duration was not longer
216 than 1 d in guard and 17 d in incubation and post-guard (Salton et al., 2015). Then, for post-
217 guard only, we calculated the overnight mass variation after returning from a foraging trip,
218 which we considered to be an estimate of chick provisioning during chick-rearing. During this
219 stage, little penguins stay only a few hours in the colony, so we assumed that all body mass loss
220 was due to chick provisioning. Body mass gained at sea was only considered when ranging from
221 700 to 1700 g and body mass change from -75 to 500 during incubation and 0 to 600 g during
222 guard and post-guard (Joly et al., 2022; Saraux et al., 2011a).

223 Using APMS, we also calculated penguins' attendance at the colony. When a penguin crosses
224 the weighbridge, it registers the timestamp, and transponder number of the penguin, allowing us
225 to know departure and arrival times of each foraging trip. We calculated departure and arrival
226 times relative to nautical dawn and dusk, respectively, to account for variation in day length
227 (Rodríguez et al., 2016).

228

229 2.6 Proxies of anthropogenic activities

230 Given that little penguins breed on land and forage at sea, we defined both on land and at
231 sea indicators of anthropogenic activities. The number of tourists present each night at the
232 penguin parade was used as an index of human activity on land, as it is the only moment where
233 penguins are exposed to tourists. At the penguin parade, visitors are allowed only at sunset
234 (when penguins come ashore, Rodríguez et al. 2016) for 50 minutes and confined to boardwalks
235 where they cannot move around the penguins. After, the colony is returned to darkness. On

236 average, around 2000 visitors attend the parade daily. Due to this setup, visitors never directly
237 interact with penguins. Number of tourists at the penguin parade was counted daily between
238 2010 and 2020. Over the studied period, artificial lighting (orange halogen lights, 3 lux) was
239 used to enhance visibility of penguins for tourists. These lights were turned on from sunset to 1.5
240 h after the arrival of the first penguins (Rodríguez et al., 2016). During the COVID lock-downs,
241 these lights were still in place but without the presence of tourists. The COVID lock-downs did
242 not affect the monitoring protocol.

243 For the activity at sea, we used the number of vessels (fishing, commercial and leisure)
244 within the little penguin foraging area (longitude 145 to 146°E, latitude 38.5 to 39.5°S) during
245 their breeding season (September to December). We used the open-source dataset from the
246 Australian Marine Safety Authority
(<https://www.operations.amsa.gov.au/Spatial/DataServices/DigitalData>) and for each vessel we
248 obtained its ID, latitude, longitude, type and timestamp. As vessels transmit their locations at
249 different time interval (from one per 15 minutes to once a day), we built daily indices by keeping
250 only one location per vessel and day: the closest to noon available. Data were available only
251 between 2014 and 2020. Information earlier than 2014 was not considered because of the lower
252 time resolution compared to later data, and data for November 2019 was missing. Hereafter, we
253 refer to the number of vessels within little penguin foraging grounds as the marine traffic
254 intensity. We calculated marine traffic UD using the same method described before for the little
255 penguins.

256

257 2.7 Statistical analysis

258 *2.7.1 Variation of anthropogenic activities*

259 Using linear models, we investigated the variation of the number of vessels in little penguins
260 foraging area and the number of tourists at the penguin parade ® between months and breeding

261 seasons. Then, using pairwise post-hoc comparison, we tested the difference between the
262 COVID breeding season (2020) and the previous ones.

263

264 *2.7.2 Spatial variation of at sea distribution and overlap with marine traffic*

265 Overlap analyses were performed using the Utilization Distribution Overlap Index (UDOI,
266 (Fieberg and Kochanny, 2005)) which quantifies the pattern of space-use as a function of the
267 product of the overlapping UDs. UDOI is equal to 0 when two UDs do not overlap and to 1 if the
268 UDs are completely overlapping and uniformly distributed. Values higher than 1 indicate higher
269 normal overlap relative to uniform space-use. UDOI were calculated using the *kerneloverlap()*
270 function from the “adehabitatHR” R package (Calenge, 2006).

271 We calculated the UD overlap at 95% of the distribution of penguins of breeding season A with
272 the little penguin distributions of all the other breeding seasons, generating a distribution of
273 UDOIs for breeding season A. We then assessed whether the observed distribution in 2020 was
274 different compared to the previous breeding seasons. We also calculated the UDOI between little
275 penguins and marine traffic. Again, we calculated UDOIs of breeding season A (little penguin)
276 with all the marine traffic data between 2014 and 2020. This was done because marine traffic
277 spatial distribution was stable throughout the studied period. We tested differences between
278 breeding seasons using generalized linear models (GLMs) with a gamma distribution. We then
279 performed post-hoc pairwise comparison to assess the significance of differences observed
280 between 2020 and the other breeding seasons.

281

282 *2.7.3 Effect of number of tourists on little penguins attendance and foraging efficiency*

283 Linear models (LMs) were used to test the effect of lock-down on (a) average departure and
284 arrival times of little penguin relative to nautical dawn and nautical dusk, respectively and (b)
285 average mass variation per day over a foraging trip, and overnight. Models were built using the
286 ‘nlme’ R package (Pinheiro et al., 2021). For both models (a and b) we considered number of

287 tourists and number of vessels as explanatory variables, and breeding stage and season as fixed
288 effects. To assess the effect sizes of both vessels and tourists counts, we standardized these data.

289

290 *2.7.4 Quantification of isotopic niche:*

291 We computed standard ellipse area corrected for small sample size and extreme values (SEAC) to
292 estimate isotopic niche width and overlap among the different breeding seasons and stages.

293 SEAC represents the isotopic niche width of 40% of typical individuals within the groups, based
294 on bivariate normal distribution. The overlap in SEAC was calculated for all pairs of breeding

295 seasons within a breeding stage following (Catry et al., 2016) where isotopic niche overlap was
296 expressed as a proportion of the area of overlap between two SEAC to its own SEAC. We also

297 computed Bayesian Standard ellipse area (SEAB) (n = 20000 iterations) to obtain credible
298 intervals (99%, 95% and 50%) for the calculated ellipses. We considered non-overlapping 95%

299 CI around SEAB as an indicator of statistically significant difference between niches width. For
300 all this analysis, we followed the method described in (Jackson et al., 2011) and the ‘SIBER’ R

301 package.

302 **3. Results**

303 3.1 Variation of anthropogenic activities

304 In 2020, during the COVID lock-downs, Phillip Island nature park remained closed for most of
305 the breeding season, resulting in an average number of tourists 10 times lower than usual (180.4
306 ± 27.9 tourists per day in 2020 vs. 1770.0 ± 20.5 on average in 2010-2019, all $p < 0.001$, figure 1,
307 supplementary table 2.A).

308 In 2020, the daily average number of vessels recorded at sea was 262 ± 8.51 . This was
309 significantly higher than the one recorded for 2014 of 212 ± 5.35 (estimate = 50.607, $t = 5.562$, p
310 < 0.001), and lower than 2018 with 297 ± 6.91 vessels (estimate = -34.279, $t = -3.767$, $p = 0.002$,
311 figure 1, supplementary table 2.B).

312

313 3.2 Spatial variation of at sea distribution and overlap with marine traffic

314 While spatial distribution of marine traffic remained similar across seasons, little penguins core
315 (50% UD) and home ranges (95% UD) showed great inter-annual variation across the studied
316 period (figure 2). We compared the overlaps of penguins distribution in 2020 (average UDOI of
317 0.86 ± 0.07) to all the other breeding seasons (average UDOI ranging from 0.58 ± 0.09 in 2015
318 to 1.09 ± 0.07 in 2014) at 95% UD. We did not find any significant difference in the overlap
319 distributions in 2020 vs any other season (supplementary table 2.C).

320 Regarding overlap with marine traffic, model selection pointed at the model with the effect of
321 the breeding season as explanatory variable as best (supplementary table 2.D). We found
322 variation in the overlap between marine traffic and little penguins' distributions (from 2014 to
323 2020). In 2020, the overlap between little penguins and marine traffic was significantly lower
324 (0.184 ± 0.009) than in 2018 (average = 0.649 ± 0.144 , estimate = 3.879, $p < 0.001$) and 2017
325 (average = 0.358 ± 0.128 , estimate = 2.627, $p < 0.001$), but higher than the one of 2015 (average
326 = 0.021 ± 0.003 , estimate = - 41.868, $p < 0.001$, supplementary table 3.D).

327

328 3.3 Effect of number of tourists and marine traffic on colony attendance

329 Little penguins left the colony on average 52.9 ± 0.5 minutes ($n = 11,116$) before nautical dawn
330 and there was no difference across seasons. The best model testing the effect of anthropogenic
331 activities on the time of departure relative to nautical dawn retained only the effect of breeding
332 stage as explanatory variable (supplementary table 2.E, p -value <0.01), with therefore no
333 significant inter-annual variations (supplementary table 3.E) and no effect of the number of
334 tourists or boats. During incubation, penguins left 31.8 minutes (95% CI [24.5; 39.0]) before
335 nautical dawn, compared to 74.9 minutes (95% CI [67.7;82.2]) during guard and 47.1 minutes
336 (95% CI [39.9;54.4]) during post-guard (figure 3A).

337 Model selection for the models testing the effect of anthropogenic activities on the time of arrival
338 relative to nautical dusk pointed at the null model as best (supplementary table 2.F), indicating
339 an absence of effect of tourists presence and marine traffic on colony attendance. Penguins
340 showed highly synchronized arrival time regardless of season or breeding stage, arriving at the
341 colony on average 8.2 ± 0.4 min after nautical dusk ($n = 11,087$, figure 3B, supplementary table
342 3.F).

343

344 3.4 Effect of number of tourists and marine traffic on foraging efficiency

345 Over a foraging trip, penguins gained on average 258.65 ± 1.75 g per day ($n = 6617$). The best
346 model testing the effect of anthropogenic activities and temporal variations on mass gained per
347 day at sea retained breeding stage and daily average number of vessels at sea as explanatory
348 variables (figure 3, supplementary table 2.G), indicating an effect of marine traffic intensity but
349 not of anthropause on foraging efficiency. Higher number of vessels was associated with lower
350 mass gain at sea for little penguins (estimate = $- 56.9 \pm 17.3$ g, $F = 10.8$, $p = 0.004$,
351 supplementary table 3.G). Predicted breeding stage mass gain were all significantly different
352 from one another ($F = 46.6$, all $p < 0.05$). During incubation, penguins gained 127.4 g (95% CI

353 [100.6;154.3]) per day, compared to 300.7 g (95% CI [274.2;327.1]) in guard, and 261.4 g (95%
354 CI [234.6;288.2]) in post-guard.

355 The average overnight mass change during post-guard, i.e. chick meal size, was of 278.6 ± 0.1 g
356 ($n = 1794$). Though the best model was the one with the average number of vessels at sea
357 (supplementary table 2.H), its effect was not significant on meal size given to the chicks
358 (estimate = $- 22.8 \pm 11.2$, $F = 4.2$, $p = 0.06$, figure 3D, supplementary table 3.H).

359

360 3.5 Quantification of isotopic niche

361 A total of 842 blood samples were collected from little penguins across the different breeding
362 stages (supplementary table 4). We observed variations in the isotopic niche values and areas at
363 different breeding stages over 10 breeding seasons (figure 4). During incubation, the SEA_B mode
364 of 2020 was 0.79 ‰^2 with 95% CI [0.48;1.25] and was significantly higher than 2 others
365 breeding seasons, 2011 (0.19 ‰^2 [0.13;0.31]) and 2015 (0.21 ‰^2 [0.14;0.34]) (figure 5). During
366 the guard stage, SEA_B was higher for 2020 (0.98 ‰^2 [0.69; 1.39]) than 2011 again (0.24 ‰^2
367 [0.17;0.33]), and 2010 (0.46 ‰^2 [0.33;0.65]). Finally, during the post-guard, the SEA_B of 2020
368 decreased (0.60 ‰^2 [0.45;0.87]). It was still significantly higher than the SEA_B of 2011 (0.29 ‰^2
369 [0.21;0.42]), but also significantly lower than the one of 2014 (1.51 ‰^2 [0.88; 2.72]). These inter
370 annual variations led to low overlap between the isotopic niches of little penguins between 2010
371 and 2020.

372 4. Discussion

373 Humans have increasingly altered natural habitats, triggering changes in movements,
374 habitat use and population dynamics in wild species (Holles et al., 2013; Margalida et al., 2014).
375 The anthropause period caused by the COVID-19 pandemic set an unprecedented opportunity to
376 study the effects of reduced human activities on the biology and ecology of a range of species
377 (Rutz et al., 2020). During the anthropause, human activity on land decreased massively in our
378 studied area, with a reduction almost by a factor 10 in the number of tourists of the Penguin
379 Parade®, Phillip Island Nature Park, Australia. Contrary to the expected (Bates et al., 2021), the
380 lock-down policy did not seem to affect the marine traffic, neither spatially nor quantitatively
381 within the penguin foraging zone within our study site in the Bass Strait. This specific setup
382 allowed us to study the effect of on land activity through a stable at-sea potential pressure
383 throughout the study period. Despite the important inter-annual variability in at-sea distribution
384 and diet of little penguins over the period 2010-2020, no effect of the anthropause was found.
385 Still, we found anthropogenic effect not linked with the anthropause. Despite the marine traffic
386 intensity stability over the studied period, thanks to our long-term dataset, we were able to
387 identify a negative relationship between marine traffic intensity and mass gained at sea per day
388 by little penguins.

389 Human activities are known to affect seabirds' physiology and behavior. Previous studies
390 showed the negative effects of anthropogenic noise (Pichegru et al., 2017), human presence
391 (Ellenberg et al., 2013), domestic animal (Ratcliffe et al., 2010), food waste (Grémillet et al.,
392 2008) and marine pollution (Trathan et al., 2015) on seabirds. A similar study (i.e., seabird in
393 parks or area without tourists due to lock-downs) found that the absence of tourists could,
394 counter-intuitively, lead to more disturbance for the seabirds, which translated in a later laying
395 date and more egg predation (Hentati-Sundberg et al., 2021), underlining the protective role
396 tourists can have for some species. We did not find such an effect in the parameters studied in
397 this paper. On land, predators of little penguins are mainly goannas, snakes and cats

398 (Colombelli-Négrel and Katsis, 2021). However, these predators are a not a threat on Phillip
399 Island, thanks to the conservation program in place (BirdLife International, 2023).

400 Still, little penguins are known to be sensitive to anthropogenic activities like human
401 presence around the nest (Colombelli-Négrel and Katsis, 2021). A recent study identified the
402 negative effect of white light sources, at night on little penguins (Costello and Colombelli-Négrel,
403 2023), but evidences are mixed since another study found the opposite (Rodríguez et al., 2018).
404 Multiple hypotheses could explain the absence of response during the anthropause in our study.
405 One could argue that the duration and/or magnitude of the anthropause was negligible to trigger
406 a response in the foraging behavior of little penguins. Plasticity being species dependent
407 (Crawford et al., 2017), more studies on little penguins would be necessary to assess the extent
408 of their plasticity in response to anthropogenic activities, and the potential different threshold
409 that could trigger a response in the studied parameters (Cairns, 1988). Long-term exposure to
410 tourists at the Penguin Parade ®, could have habituated little penguins to anthropogenic
411 disturbance (Rodríguez et al., 2016). Our results underline the positive outcome of management
412 and conservation actions put in place to mitigate human-wildlife co-existence. Similarly, several
413 successful habitat restoration or predator removal programs have been carried out to aid
414 conservation on both marine and terrestrial species (Moor et al., 2022, Jones et al., 2008).

415 To our knowledge, this paper provides the first empirical assessment of the negative
416 effect of marine traffic on little penguins' foraging success during their breeding period. Our
417 study underlines that the at-sea disturbances are more important than those on land when it
418 comes to affect little penguins foraging. Our spatial analysis revealed an overlap between little
419 penguins and marine traffic in the Bass strait. However, in the Bass strait, fisheries represent
420 only a small proportion (< 1 %) of the marine traffic in comparison with cargo (50-60 %), tanker
421 (10-20 %), and passenger vessels (5-8 % supplementary figure 1). It is therefore unlikely that the
422 observed effect is due to a competition with fisheries for food. Collisions with leisure boats, for
423 example, can represent a high mortality source for little penguins (Cannell et al. 2016). Increased

424 traffic, especially of big cargo ships, leads to noise pollution affecting the behaviour and
425 reproduction of marine predators (Pichegru et al., 2022, Pirotta et al., 2022) and the distribution
426 of preys (Ivanova et al., 2020). Another sentinel species of the Bass Strait, the Australian fur seal
427 (*Arctocephalus pusillus doriferus*), showed behavioural changes (more alertness behaviour)
428 when in the presence of vessels (Speakman et al. 2020). More investigations are needed to fully
429 understand how marine traffic impacts little penguins to be implemented on marine spatial
430 planning.

431 Using quantitative information about human activity, like the number of tourists, rather
432 than qualitative one (e.g., comparing lock-down season vs past observed trends) is key to be able
433 to compare study results and assess the shape of the response of wildlife to anthropogenic
434 activities. Indeed, many studies fail to properly quantify anthropogenic activities, and only
435 compared “COVID breeding season” with other breeding seasons before and/or after (Gordo et
436 al., 2021; Hentati-Sundberg et al., 2021). While informative, this approach does not allow to
437 properly disentangle anthropogenic pressure from seasonal and environmental variations.
438 Incorporating a quantification of anthropogenic pressure in our models (i.e., number of tourists
439 and vessels) allowed us to disentangle the natural inter- and intra-annual variations from
440 anthropogenic pressure. Our study highlighted that long-term monitoring studies are key to be
441 able to disentangle such effects. Occupying high trophic levels, sentinel species inform us about
442 changes happening within ecosystems (Hazen et al. 2019). Therefore, long-term monitoring of
443 such species, like the little penguin, can allow us to identify such changes at longer time scales
444 and implement conservation actions (Duffy et al., 2002). For instance, the conservation actions
445 associated with the return of wolves (*Canis lupus*) in the Yellowstone national park, triggered
446 consequences all along the trophic chain of this ecosystem (Berger & Smith, 2005).

447 The effect of the anthropauses caused by the COVID related lock-downs on little
448 penguins’ ecology during the breeding might be negligible compared to the ones induced by
449 long-term environmental variations and global changes (Joly et al., 2022). Other significant

450 effects found in our study are mostly related to intra and inter-annual variations. Thanks to long-
451 term monitoring and online data availability, we were able to have a detailed picture of the
452 impact of anthropogenic activities over the 10 breeding seasons. Species showing high plasticity
453 and therefore quickly responding to reduced pressures during anthropauses are likely to use that
454 same plasticity in the other way when anthropogenic activities increase again. Such punctual
455 changes could be buffered by phenotypic plasticity and unlikely to change population trends
456 compared to long-term variations (Gordo et al., 2021).

457 In conclusion, we did not detect any positive or negative effect of COVID-19 lock-downs
458 on the little penguin breeding ecology. Behavioral variation during penguins' breeding cycle
459 was mostly due to the inter- and intra-annual variation. Increased marine traffic can affect
460 foraging efficiency of little penguins. Still, as seabirds live at the interface between sea and land,
461 more information needs to be gathered on the mechanisms behind the effects of marine activities
462 on little penguins' foraging. Our paper is of example of how conservation actions can be
463 implemented to manage human-wildlife co-existence. Given the variability in the responses to
464 anthropogenic activities and the fast changes of the marine environment, maintaining and
465 developing long-term monitoring sites and studies are keys for guiding conservation policies.
466 This will help scientists and stakeholders to better distinguish between environmental and
467 anthropogenic effects on wild species.

468 **Authors contributions**

469 Conceptualization : AC, YRC, AK

470 Data curation : BD, MC, NJ, AK

471 Analysis : BD

472 Writing : BD, MC

473 Review of draft : all authors

474 Supervision : MC, AK, AC

475

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483 Committee with a research permit issued by the Department of Environment, Land, Water and
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485

486 **Conflict of interest:**

487 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

488

489 **Data availability statement:**

490 Sample dataset and all R codes used to manipulate and analyze the data used are available at
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734 **Figure 1:** Evolution of anthropogenic activities in the studied area. (A) Daily number of tourists
 735 at the penguin parade ® between 2010 and 2020. (B) Daily number of vessels at sea in the
 736 foraging area of little penguins between 2014 and 2020. Asterisks represent statistical
 737 significance of post-hoc comparisons between 2020 (lock-down season) and the others (2010-
 738 2019, ** = $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$).

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of little penguins and marine traffic between 2014 and 2020. The black dot represents the studied colony in Phillip Island.

Figure 3: Anthropogenic activities effect on APMS-derived parameters. (A) Departure time relatively to nautical dawn, and (B) Arrival time relatively to nautical dusk of little penguins at the colony depending on the number of tourists. Effect of the number of vessels on the (C) Mass gain per day at sea and (D) Meal mass given to the chicks at the colony. Colored points represent a season average, and white points the overall mean with its SE. Dashed lines represent the 95% CI around model predictions.

Figure 4: Isotopic niche of little penguins between 2010 and 2020, across different breeding stages: A. Incubation, B. Guard and C. Post-guard. Ellipses represent the corrected standard ellipses of each niche (40% of the individuals).

Figure 5: Standard ellipses' area of little penguin's isotopic niches between 2010 and 2020 during different breeding stages: A. Incubation, B. Guard and C. Post-guard. Black dots represent the mode of the Bayesian standard ellipse area, and error bars the confidence intervals at 50, 95 and 99%. Circles represent the corrected standard ellipse areas.